

ERA CHAIR IN DATA SPACES FOR CULTURAL HERITAGE

HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-TALENTS-01

D6.1: Plan for dissemination and exploitation, including communication activities

Work Package 6

Type of document:	Deliverable
Dissemination level:	Public
Lead beneficiary:	UNISOFIA
Authors:	Seamus Ross, Milena Dobрева, Sylvia Ilieva
Version:	1.0
Due Date of document:	31-08-2023
Delivery Date of document:	31-08-2023

Document Control Page	
Title	D6.1: Plan for dissemination and exploitation, including communication activities
Creator	Seamus Ross, Milena Dobрева
Description	Description of the dissemination and communication activities within DISPATCHES.
Publisher	DISPATCHES
Contributors	Seamus Ross, Milena Dobрева, Orlin Kouzov, Sylvia Ilieva
Publication date	31 August 2023
Type	Text
Language	en-GB
Rights	Copyright Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski", GATE Institute
Audience	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential <input type="checkbox"/> Classified
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> In Progress <input type="checkbox"/> For Review <input type="checkbox"/> For Approval <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Approved

Document History

Version	Date	Contributor	Comments
v0.1	26/04/23	Creation of document	Milena Dobрева
v0.2	31/07/23	Content write-up	Milena Dobрева
v0.3	7/08/23	Further edits	Seamus Ross
v0.4	10/08/23	Draft sent for internal review	Milena Dobрева
v0.5	25/08/23	Revisions	Seamus Ross
V0.6	30/08/23	Quality check	Orlin Kouzov
v1.0	31/08/23	Final version	Sylvia Ilieva

Executive summary

To ensure the success of a research project, it is crucial to effectively communicate and disseminate its objectives and findings to key stakeholders. This is especially essential for projects from the Widening calls, which are not only intended to strengthen the research culture in countries with poor research performance, but should also assist in enhancing the visibility of new successful academic institutions.

As data spaces are still being conceptualized and developed, dissemination and communication duties within the novel domain of common European data spaces, and the data space for cultural heritage in particular, are particularly challenging.

This document's purpose is to define the dissemination and communication plan for the duration of the DISPATCHES project, as well as the scheduled activities for promoting awareness of the project's research findings. The deliverable addresses a broad variety of topics, including the purpose and scope of the document, a concise overview of the project, a list of target audiences for communication, and a plan for the project's dissemination and communication activities and channels. In this plan, dissemination refers to sharing information with professionals and scientists, while communication refers to sharing information with broader audiences.

This document outlines the framework of activities and channels that will be developed and utilized to disseminate project results to the DISPATCHES target audiences.

The plan also establishes the initial scope of project exploitation activities, which will be expanded upon in D2.5 (plan for sustainability).

Contents

1	Project Introduction.....	7
2	Deliverable purpose, scope, and context	8
2.1	Document status.....	10
2.2	Deliverable structure	10
2.3	Relationship with other documents	11
3	Project Overview.....	13
3.1	Project Ambition and Vision.....	13
3.2	Project Objectives	13
3.3	The Advisory Board.....	14
4	Dissemination & Communication Plan	14
4.1	Objectives	14
4.2	Key messages and narratives.....	16
4.3	Target audiences.....	17
4.4	Key Performance Indicators of DISPATCHES Dissemination Activities	20
5	Dissemination & Communication Channels and Tools	20
5.1	Project website	21
5.2	DISPATCHES Visual Material.....	21
5.3	Social Media Channels & Planning	22
5.4	Conferences Workshops Meetings	22
5.5	Publications.....	25
5.6	Press releases and coverage.....	28
6	Exploitation framework	28
7	Conclusion.....	29
	Appendix 1. IAB ToR.....	30
	Appendix 2. IAB Composition	31

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
CH	Cultural heritage
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DCH	Digital cultural heritage
DMP	Data Management Plan
DS	Data Space
EAB	Expert Advisory Board
EAF	Europeana Aggregators Forum
ENA	Europeana Network Association
GLAM	Galleries, libraries, archives, museums
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
UNISOFIA	Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski"
WP	Work Package

List of Tables

Table 1. Key aspects of communication, dissemination and sustainability in DISPATCHES	15
Table 2. Key communication messages	17
Table 3. An Overview of Target Audiences.....	18
Table 4. Dissemination KPIs and metrics	20
Table 5 Conferences for reaching DISPATCHES target communities	23
Table 6. Contribution to events within the first six months of the project.....	23
Table 7. Highest ranking journals in information science based on SCOPUS data.....	26
Table 8. Journals publishing articles in the domain of digital libraries	27
Table 9. Exploitation benefits for key target groups	28

List of Figures

Figure 1. DISPATCHES logo in two colours and project colour palette	21
Figure 2. DISPATCHES sample banners.....	22

1 Project Introduction

DISPATCHES aspires to establish an ERA Chair in data spaces for cultural heritage at Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski"'s GATE- Big Data for Smart Society Institute. GATE Institute is a Big Data and Artificial Intelligence Center of Excellence and one of the International Data Spaces Association's ten European data space hubs. The European data space for cultural heritage is in its initial stages. A program of focused research and strong cross-sector engagement will contribute to the ongoing transformation in the digital cultural heritage domain. GATE's current portfolio does not include digital cultural heritage, but it can contribute knowledge in data spaces from other domains, such as smart cities and intelligent government, to this sector. DISPATCHES intends to:

- Deliver a substantial boost in the GATE Institute's expertise by adding data spaces for digital cultural heritage to its portfolio.
- Increase the number of high quality staff members engaged in data space research by 9%.
- Enhance the visibility of the GATE Institute in the domain through at least 30 new high quality research-led publications.
- Support the structural reforms in the host institution, which would further help to strengthen its existing excellence in data spaces and/or cultural heritage research.
- Contribute to reversing the brain drain by offering opportunities for early stage researchers, including 5 PhD students to conduct and press forward with fundamental research.
- Demonstrate the various aspects of open science and sharing with the wider University community especially within the Humanities where the open science concept is less well known and deployed.
- Contribute to efforts for creating European data space in cultural heritage.
- Establish the unit as a permanent centre by the end of the project to consolidate the currently dispersed digital cultural heritage expertise at the host institution, enhance the GATE Institute's excellence and the diversity in its staff.

Setting up an ERA Chair delivering pioneering research requires a combination of thorough planning and a flexible strategy for identifying newly emerging avenues for communication and dissemination. New research domains do not enjoy the availability of clear communication channels with established publication venues and events and

this is a major challenge towards the planning.

To enhance the impact and improve the exploitation potential of DISPATCHES, the communication and dissemination (C&D) plan aims to raise general awareness about the project, to target key audiences and stakeholders, to foster the academic discourse in a new research domain and to assist the release of scientifically and commercially significant results.

2 Deliverable purpose, scope, and context

The objectives of this deliverable are twofold. First, it intends to provide an overview of the various activities the initiative will undertake over the next five years to promote the work of the ERA Chair to specific target audiences. Second, this document will serve as a guide for the planning of dissemination, communication, and awareness activities throughout DISPATCHES.

Four levels of effort are to be developed: (i) dissemination to public authorities and policymakers; (ii) dissemination of scientific and technical information; (iii) dissemination and communication to GLAMs; and (iv) dissemination and communication for the general public.

Although communication activities may utilize similar outreach channels, the intensity, tone, and key messages must be systematically followed and tailored to the specific audiences.

The plan also establishes the initial scope of project exploitation activities, which will be expanded upon in D2.5 (plan for sustainability).

Over 2023-2028, the project aims to:

- Inform the **research community** of the latest developments taking place within DISPATCHES and how the project may effect various research fields.

The main challenge here is not to deliver and communicate ‘shallow’ interdisciplinarity. Data spaces are a complex concept and the new Chair will be interdisciplinary in composition bringing together researchers capable of delivering breakthroughs not only through generating new knowledge underpinning the novel complex ecosystem in the CH domain, but also by shifting the knowledge in domains such as information management, user behaviour, complex digital objects’ rights management, interoperability between data spaces, to name just a few.

- Communicate project progress, technologies, and results (outside the consortium and research community) to the **cultural heritage, education and technical communities** as well as the general public and how it may affect their lives in the future.

The main challenge here is to create clear picture of the novel aspects the data space is bringing to life. Being yet another tool of the digital transformation, it is still difficult to explain clearly how it differs from older infrastructures and what benefits it brings to different stakeholders.

- Engage different key audiences (see Section 4.3) and raise awareness of the project, its objectives, and its achievements and how they benefit or can exploit the project (see Section 6).

As the context of building the ERA Chair is creating a new department, the key approach here is to build a strategic narrative which does not limit to what the new department is doing, but also communicates the human side – who is at the helm, how they build their team and what is this group striving to achieve.

- Raise the interest of professionals from the CH sectors and technological companies in to contribute to activities such as secondments, master classes and summer schools.

The project's progress is impossible without creating a strong community interested in and actively participating in project events and secondments. These activities are not integrated into the project plan as knowledge transfer 'inside-out' but as means for integrating diversified contributions, which would boost the research within DISPATCHES.

- Ensure the widest dissemination possible of the project's results to various stakeholders and share best practices stemming from the project, useful practical tools and insights via various channels.

The right channels and tone are of special importance here – the project does not plan its C&D activities as repetitive messages to different audiences but create a style of originality and novelty in its dissemination.

- Help to establish liaisons/synergies with other related projects to exchange knowledge and best practices.

The data space domain is growing and it is essential to liaise and create synergies with other projects, especially those which work on the practical development of the data space for cultural heritage (DS4CH), the European Cloud for Cultural Heritage as well as other relevant research proposals.

- Prepare for a successful exploitation of project results.

To continue its successful work, the newly established team at the host institutions will need to take into the future results from DISPATCHES which contribute to the competitiveness and allow to attract further funding.

- Contribute to the development of a sustainable department.

To continue its successful work, the newly established team at the host institutions will need to take into the future results from DISPATCHES which contribute to the competitiveness and allow to attract further funding.

- Contribute to the proliferation of open science practices in digital humanities.

DISPATCHES is ideally positioned to promote open science practices related to different Humanities disciplines. Humanities are lagging behind other academic areas in the adoption of open science. This is yet another area where DISPATCHES need clear communication in order to deliver impact.

2.1 Document status

The deliverable is public in nature. It is also intended for internal use to assist the project team in collecting and reporting on dissemination and communication activities.

2.2 Deliverable structure

The DISPATCHES DMP is divided into the following sections:

- Section 3 – Project overview
- Section 4 – Dissemination and Communication Plan
- Section 5 – Dissemination and communication channels and tools

- Section 6 – Exploitation framework

2.3 Relationship with other documents

This deliverable is a part of the WP6 Maximize Impact: Communication, Engagement, Dissemination, and Exploitation work package.

Task T6.1: Dissemination and Communication plan and activities connects and prepares the Dissemination and Communication plan.

First, the mission concentrates on delivering the plan for dissemination and exploitation, which includes M6 communication activities. The plan will detail the target audience and stakeholder groups' stakeholder communities, communication channels, value propositions, and other engagement strategies. The plan will be devised by the ERA Chair with the assistance of the GATE Institute's Public Engagement Manager.

Second, the task consolidates the communication activities that are aimed at the largest audiences and will be carried out with the assistance of Bulgarian National Television (GATE has a history of collaborating with it). The communication activities will include Awareness Raising Campaigns that incorporate brief TV films, press releases, and newspaper and magazine articles. Users-appealing formats, such as videos and infographics, will be routinely generated and distributed via DISPATCHES's communication channels.

These materials will focus on illustrating the effects of DISPATCHES's work rather than providing technical descriptions of activities.

As part of the Chair's and its team's initial visibility campaign, the ERA Chair will participate in a number of high-profile events.

Thirdly, the mission involves dissemination activities that target researchers from diverse domains, including DCH, data spaces, artificial intelligence, and knowledge management. Plans for WP3, WP4, and WP5 publications all presume open access publications. This task's purpose would be to assist the ERA Chair team in providing lists of recommended publication venues and disseminating relevant high-profile inquiries. DISPATCHES also encourages participation in national and international conferences and other events, and will promote opportunities for cross-sectoral dissemination at conferences for cultural heritage professionals, IT company specialists, and media professionals.

In addition, the endeavor will include the organization and implementation of open review practices for GATE-organized research events with paper submissions.

The main objectives within the task are aimed to:

- Ensure wide dissemination of the project's results to potentially interested.
- Communicate the project progress to the cultural, social and technical community and in the general society.
- Establish liaisons / synergies with other related projects and develop the existing ecosystem of stakeholders.

In future revisions, C&D need as well to integrate indicators which had been established during the development of the Research Agenda of DISPATCHES.

3 Project Overview

3.1 Project Ambition and Vision

DiSPAtCHes seeks to establish an ERA Chair in data spaces for cultural heritage at Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski" GATE Institute Big Data for Smart Society. GATE Institute is a Big Data and Artificial Intelligence Center of Excellence and one of the eight European data space centers of the International Data Spaces Association. The European data space for cultural heritage is in its infancy, and a program of targeted research and robust cross-sector collaboration will contribute to the ongoing transformation of the digital cultural heritage domain.

- GATE does not currently work with digital cultural heritage, but it can apply its knowledge of data spaces from other areas, such as smart cities, to this domain. GATE seeks to entice Seamus Ross, presently a professor at the University of Toronto in Canada, as a potential chair candidate in order to:
- establish and nurture a team of researchers investigating research challenges associated (e.g., user enablers and data enablers) with the development of the European cultural heritage data space;
- consolidate the dispersed institutional expertise in digital cultural heritage;
- build European and International cross-sectoral initiatives to promote inclusion of cultural heritage data sets in shared data spaces and their use;
- deliver a series of research-led summer schools, international masterclasses, doctoral research opportunities, and mobility exchanges to foster research into data spaces;
- cultivate research collaborations to seek resources to extend the nature of the research that is conducted under this initiative.
- demonstrate the various aspects of open science and sharing with the wider University community especially within the Humanities where open science is underused.

Establishing the unit as a permanent one by the end of the project will help to consolidate the currently dispersed digital cultural heritage expertise at the host institution, enhance the GATE Institute's excellence and the diversity of its staff, and contribute to the creation of a European data space for cultural heritage.

Since this is the first academic department dedicated to research supporting the development of modern data spaces, the initiative must establish and execute a vision that has the potential for global impact.

3.2 Project Objectives

The vision of DISPATCHES in establishing the first department focusing on providing excellent research on data spaces for cultural heritage will be achieved by reaching these complementary objectives:

- Implement structural changes to achieve excellence on a sustainable basis.
- Revert the brain drain by supporting early career and experienced talents to explore unknown personal territories for professional development.
- Improve links between sectors (academia, business, cultural heritage sector, media industries, non-governmental sectors).
- Foster better exploitation of existing research infrastructures.
- Provide a best practice in using all instruments of Open Science.

3.3 The Advisory Board

The International Advisory Board of the ERA Chair DISPATCHES includes a group of visionary leaders from a number of domains relevant to the Chair. The role of the Advisory Board would be to contribute to the refinement of the Research Agenda which will guide the research within the newly established department, and to add visibility to the ERA Chair and its activities.

The Terms of Reference of the Advisory Board are presented in Appendix 1 and the list of members is presented in Appendix 2.

4 Dissemination & Communication Plan

This is the initial version of the C&D strategy of DISPATCHES project. It is based on the project proposal and reflects deliverables and KPIs from the contract

4.1 Objectives

The dissemination objective related to DISPATCHES is to make its intellectual assets (research papers, datasets, architectures, methodologies, teaching materials, etc.) easily available to the public and stakeholder groups

The **objectives of the communication activities** are as follows:

- to offer appropriate visibility to the ERA Chair team;
- to motivate researchers, educators, CH professionals, policymakers to follow DISPATCHES activities and engage with opportunities to contribute (secondments, events);
- to communicate with other data space projects and initiatives and to join forces in building the data space for cultural heritage.

The **objectives of the dissemination activities** are as follows:

- Raising the public awareness of the DISPATCHES activities;
- Promoting activities and foster engagement with different types of stakeholders;
- Preparing the hosting Institute for continuity of activities;
- Establishing new partnerships and collaborations.

Focusing on the above objectives, the C&D strategy answers the following questions:

- What are the specific messages, used for content and communication? (Section 3.2)
- What types of visuals convey the messages? (Section 3.2)
- Whom does it need to be delivered to and what communication channels should be used? (Section 3.3)
- What key performance indicators (KPIs) capture the success of the D&C activities (Section 4.4.)¹

DISPATCHES takes a proactive approach and seeks to reach the relevant stakeholders for each of these activities, as shown in Table 5. It will deliver its plan for communication, dissemination, and exploitation as D6.1 in M6. The plan will be continuously revised, and the team will cultivate a culture of recognizing and sharing opportunities as they arise.

Table 1. Key aspects of communication, dissemination and sustainability in DISPATCHES

<i>Impact details</i>	<i>Communication</i>	<i>Dissemination</i>	<i>Sustainability</i>
<i>Focus</i>	Promote DISPATCHES and its results	Make DISPATCHES results public	Make concrete use of DISPATCHES results; create a unit which will continue existing after the project ends.
<i>Keywords</i>	Inform, Attract, Engage	Open science, Knowledge and results	Commercial, Societal, Policy-related
<i>Promote</i>	Impact stories: how did the project help answer a societal need?	Excellent research: what challenges were tackled, and what solutions were coined?	Useful, practical knowledge: how to transform the practice in different sectors?

¹ For the time being we are outlying the KPIs - their delivery will be followed closely in future C&D deliverables.

Target audience	Cultural heritage professionals, Data space technologists, Researchs and students, Citizens, the media, stakeholders	Academics, industries, policy makers, NGOs (across sectors that benefit from the research outcomes)	Authorities, CCI, SMEs, civil society, other data spaces
How?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Clear messages. – Good use of appropriate channels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Journal publications – Datasets – EOSC and IR for datasets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Prototypes sharing – Knowledge, skills, data
When?	M1-M60	M7-after the project end	M37 – beyond the project
Why?	<p>Attract best international and national talent</p> <p>Engage with stakeholders</p> <p>Generate a network which will help the exploitation (test market demand)</p>	<p>Maximise academic results' impact</p> <p>Make results a common good and contribute to developing the research in data spaces further</p> <p>Contribute to the state-of-the-art knowledge in the domain</p>	<p>Answer societal needs (example – saving cultural data from Ukraine)</p> <p>Foster innovation</p>
Tools	<p>Visual identity</p> <p>Project website</p> <p>Social media channels</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Attractive formats – videos, infographics</p>	<p>Conference presentations</p> <p>OA publications</p> <p>Participation in business and CH professionals events</p> <p>Workshops</p>	<p>Summer schools</p> <p>Brainstorming inter-sectorial workshops</p> <p>Technological exploitation (patents)</p>
Key media partners in Bulgaria	Bulgarian National Television		<p>Ministry of Innovation;</p> <p>Ministry of Education and Science;</p> <p>CLaDA-BG</p>

4.2 Key messages and narratives

The key messages for DISPATCHES capture the essence of the initiative while also developing and expanding upon the key messages in the GATE Institute's Communication Plan.

Table 2 provides a summary of these messages.

Table 2. Key communication messages

Key message	Description
DISPATCHES is the first academic department focusing on data spaces for CH	<i>This message positions the ERA Chair as a first specialized unit globally.</i>
DISPATCHES fosters innovative research in data spaces for cultural heritage	<i>Look at the outcomes fo DISPATCHES to follow the state of the art in the data space research.</i>
DISPATCHES innovates	<i>DISPATCHES offers novel and needed research on data spaces for cultural heritage.</i>
DISPATCHES educates	<i>DISPATCHES offers plenty of opportunities to upskill the cultural heritage professionals and works with a cohort of PhD students.</i>
DISPATCHES connects	<i>DISPATCHES brings together technological, heritage and academic partners to expedite and expand the work on data spaces for cultural heriatage.</i>
DISPATCHES contributes to the proliferation of open science	<i>DISPATCHES operates in a culture of open science and spreads this experience in Bulgaria.</i>

4.3 Target audiences

Due to the nature of this project as a single-contractor endeavor, internal communication occurs within a small team, and the primary objective is to disseminate information and engage external stakeholders. Among the most important audiences that DISPATCHES must reach are:

Cultural heritage professionals

Acting as data providers, data resource users, and data access enablers.

Europeana

The flagship European infrastructure on digital cultural heritage content.

Data space technologists

Developers, information architects, tool-makers, policy makers.

Researchers and Students

Those engaged with digital heritage data sets and those researching data spaces for the cultural heritage.

Citizen Scientists

Individuals with an interest in studying and using digital heritage data sets.

Governmental and policy bodies

Developing policies. Reporting to the EC on the progress in developing local measures supporting the data space for cultural heritage.

In Table 3 below the target groups that we aim to reach are being identified along with the proposed activities to reach them.

Table 3. An Overview of Target Audiences

Target Groups	Key institutions for outreach to this group	Message(s) to be communicated	Key Channels and Activities	Main impact
Cultural heritage professionals	Museums, archives, galleries, libraries, audio-visual archives. Specialists from cultural and creative industries. (CCIs)	Raise awareness. Stimulate interest in project activities. Encourage to use and validate DISPATCHES project outcomes.	Website, curated email content, cultural heritage and digital content workshops/conferences/masterclasses/ Summer schools/exhibitions/public discussions/professional fairs, social media, promotional videos, scientific publications, articles in magazines, Press releases, newspaper interviews	Local, National, European, International
Europeana	Europeana Foundation (EF), Europeana Aggregators Forum (EAF), Europeana Network Association (ENA)	Research outcomes relevant to the development of the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage	Involving a representative in the Advisory board. Direct updates to Europeana pillars (EF, ENA, EAF). Europeana online and face to face events. Writing blogs for Europeana Pro. Potential support for a national group supporting Europeana's efforts in the data space domain.	European
Researchers and students	Research and competence centres in areas of cultural heritage and	Establishment of liaison with other centers of excellence, targeting at initiatives and creation of	Joint events, website, social media, communication material	National, European

	eInfrastructures. Computer and information science departments working on digital heritage.	synergies.		
Data space technologists	Institutions developing other data spaces (business, academia)	Establishment of liaison with other initiatives and creation of synergies. Discussing potential collaboration on relevant use cases.	Joint events, website, social media interactions, communication material.	European
Citizen scientists	Via cultural heritage institutions supporting citizen science; citizen science projects and accelerators (e.g. IMPETUS4CS). ²	Raise awareness, stimulate interest in cultural heritage and relevance of values in contemporary time. Support those who are already working on relevant initiatives.	Events with public participation, website, social media, communication material, vlogs.	National, European
Governmental and Policy bodies, Agencies for Culture	Nationally: Ministry of culture	Raise awareness, exchange info, communicate importance of (common) values in policy making. Support the delivery on the large-scale digitization project within the National Recovery Plan.	Website, Press releases, events. White paper for ministries elsewhere.	National, European

² <https://impetus4cs.eu/>

4.4 Key Performance Indicators of DISPATCHES Dissemination Activities

The following table provides measurable indicators of the project's dissemination activities and sets a basis for cumulative reporting on communication and dissemination activities.

Table 4. Dissemination KPIs and metrics

Dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)			
Tool	Type	Metrics	Coverage
DISPATCHES website	Quantitative, Online	Number of visits	Worldwide
		Number of downloads of papers and datasets	
Social Media	Quantitative, Online	Number of followers – X	Worldwide
		Number of followers – linkedin	
		Number of posts per platform and engagement metrics	
Journal publications (International Referred Journals)	Quantitative	Number of publications	Worldwide
DISPATCHES participation in conferences, workshops and other events including	Qualitative in terms of participation increasing	Number of conferences noting also the key audiences and the number of participants	Worldwide
DISPATCHES organisation of summer schools, masterclasses and a final conference	Quantitative	As per DoW	Europe
DISPATCHES videos/vlogs/short documentaries distributed through social media	Quantitative	Number of produced videos/vlogs	Europe
Co-operation with other initiatives	Quantitative	Signing memoranda of understanding with relevant stakeholders	National
Webinars	Quantitative	Number of webinars	Europe
Press Releases	Quantitative	Total number (at least one per year)	Europe
		Number of media reappearances	

5 Dissemination & Communication Channels and Tools

To reach the audiences outlined in the preceding section of this document, DISPATCHES will use a variety of tools and channels to communicate its messages and deliver a consistent brand identity.

5.1 Project website

The official project website is the most essential online communication instrument because it organizes information about the project's objectives and progress. The DISPATCHES project website was made available to the public on August 29, 2023, and is accessible at <https://dispatches.bg> and <http://eudispatches.eu>³

Detailed information on the website and its structure and sections is provided within the deliverable D6.3.

5.2 DISPATCHES Visual Material

The project will use for its visual materials the project logo (Fig.1). Some banner samples are presented on Fig. 2.

Figure 1. DISPATCHES logo in two colours and project colour palette

³ We are trying to acquire the domain name of dispatches.eu, but this appears to have been purchased last August by a domain name broker. We are in negotiation with them.

Figure 2. DISPATCHES sample banners

5.3 Social Media Channels & Planning

Various considerations must be taken into account when selecting the social media channels that will assist in attaining the DISPATCHES objectives of visibility and stakeholder engagement.

YouTube and Facebook are the most popular social media platforms in Bulgaria, but policymakers have recently favored X (the rebranded Twitter). LinkedIn is a popular platform for cultural heritage professionals, and Pinterest is gaining prominence among institutions that can share visual content.

Taking advantage of the channels GATE Institute – the host of DISPATCHES – is using, the project team has decided to maintain a presence on LinkedIn and on X, with the possibility of adding Pinterest and/or Instagram in the second year of the project, when there will be an abundance of original imagery to share.

5.4 Conferences | Workshops | Meetings

The greatest obstacle for DISPATCHES is the interdisciplinary nature of its work, which necessitates reaching diverse communities active in technological domains (eInfrastructures, data management, and user behavior) and heritage domains (digital heritage). This necessitates

participation in the events of various communities. Following is a list of established conference series that will be considered for the dissemination of DISPATCHES results.

Table 5 Conferences for reaching DISPATCHES target communities

Conference	Community
CIDOC conference	Museum community
DARIAH annual conference (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH))	Digital humanities
Europeana annual conference	Digital heritage, data space
EVA (Electronic Visualisation and the Arts) conferences	Arts, digital humanities and arts
ICA (International Council of Archives) annual conference	Archival community
ICADL (International Conference of Asian Digital Libraries)	Digital libraries
IDSA (International Data Space Association) events	Data space community
IFLA (International Federation of Library Associations) annual congress	Library community
International Conference on Digital Transformation in Culture and Education	Digital culture
JCDL (Joint Conference of Digital Libraries)	Digital libraries
TPDL (Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries)	Digital libraries

Within the first six months of its work, DISPATCHES was mentioned in a number of talks and training events in Bulgaria and abroad. For this stage of the project, the aim was to create awareness of the domain and the opportunities the project will offer in the future.

Table 6. Contribution to events within the first six months of the project

Date	Type of event	Title	Contributor (ERA chair or GATE staff member)	Relevant community	Location
24/03/23	Expert meeting, focus group	Data spaces for cultural heritage	Seamus Ross a key speaker	Digital heritage, Europeana	online
22-28/04/2023	Seminar, workshop	Workshop on Open Innovation collaborations	An exploratory workshop discussing how academia and	Young researchers, citizen scientists,	Kea, Greece

		between Academia and cultural heritage organisations (CHOs)	cultural heritage organisations can collaborate for open innovation initiatives. Milena Dobрева presented open innovation and data spaces. Relevant to DISPATCHES.	small cultural institutions	
27/05/2023	Conference	The New Life of an Old and Rare books	Milena Dobрева gave a talk entitled "How to read a book in the data space?" which was an exploratory journey into the use cases relevant to an end user interested in digitised old printed books.	Librarians	Belgrade, Serbia
29/05/2023	Seminar, workshop	Citizen Science in Cultural Heritage: practices and digital technologies	Citizen participation is a growing trend in digital heritage. Milena Dobрева gave a talk on how a small museum in Bulgaria is embarking on this route. This is relevant to the larger domain of data spaces in cultural heritage.	Heritage professionals	Athens and online
7/6/2023	Expert meeting, focus group	DARIAH Scientific Board	The meeting discussed the latest trends related to innovation in digital humanities. Milena Dobрева joined as a board member and discussed the	Digital humanities experts	online

			current efforts in data spaces.		
16/06/2023	Expert meeting, focus group	Internal meeting for Europeana selected experts	Online	Europeana	Online
23-25 August 2023	Summer school	ASTRA summer school on Bibliographic Data Management	The summer school brings together PhD students and librarians interested in modern trends of librarianship. Milena Dobrova presented the introductory module on current trends including datafication, data space for cultural heritage and FAIR principles in cultural heritage data management.	PHD students, librarians	Sibiu, Romania

5.5 Publications

Within a new cross-disciplinary domain, Data spaces for cultural heritage, finding the right publication venues is a challenging task because the research outputs need to reach the right communities with unclear publication footprint.

Publication in peer-reviewed scientific periodicals is a key strategy for reaching the scientific audiences targeted by DISPATCHES and disseminating the knowledge gained through research.

An initial consideration is to submit articles to the most prestigious and high-ranking journals in information science (see Table 7).

Table 7. Highest ranking journals in information science based on SCOPUS⁴ data

Title	CiteScore	Highest percentile and domain
International Journal of Information Management	41.9	99% Computer Networks and Communications
Foundations and Trends in Information Retrieval	38.9	99% Information Systems
Information Fusion	38.6	99% Hardware and Architecture
Journal of Strategic Information Systems	31.0	99% Information Systems
Journal of Big Data Open Access	23.9	99% Hardware and Architecture
AI Open Open Access	22.5	99% Computer Science Applications
IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics	22.4	99% Control and Systems Engineering
IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics	22.3	99% Computer Science Applications
IEEE Network	19.9	98% Computer Networks and Communications
MIS Quarterly: Management Information Systems	18.7	98% Computer Science Applications
Big Data Mining and Analytics Open Access	17.7	97% Computer Science Applications
IEEE Internet of Things Journal	17.4	97% Signal Processing
Journal of Service Research	17.2	99% Sociology and Political Science
European Journal of Information Systems	17.0	99% Library and Information Sciences
Applied Computing and Informatics Open Access	16.3	97% Computer Science Applications
Information Systems Journal	16.3	96% Computer Networks and Communications
Information and Management	15.3	95% Management Information Systems
Information Processing and Management	14.8	99% Media Technology

⁴ <https://www.scopus.com/>

Another approach of selecting the right publishing venues is to concentrate on the periodicals that publish extensively on the technological support for digital heritage. These are journals from the domain of the digital library. Table 8 provides a list of the most prominent journals in this field in terms of publication density. The table lists the journals publishing most frequently articles on digital library research and is adapted from a study of Mahadevagoula and Pacithrabai.⁵

Table 8. Journals publishing articles in the domain of digital libraries

Sources	H-index	Number of published articles over 10 years
Library Philosophy and Practice	6	135
Digital Library Perspectives	9	88
Library Hi Tech	11	77
Electronic Library	15	73
International Journal on Digital Libraries	8	42
Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology	12	37
Proceedings of the Association for Information Science and Technology	12	37
Journal of Documentation	8	35

Additional high-ranked journal across relevant disciplines (Data science, Cultural heritage informatics, Cultural heritage) include:

- Journal of Cultural Heritage Management and Sustainable Development
- International Journal of Heritage Studies
- Journal of Cultural Heritage
- Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage (DAACH)
- Museum Management and Curatorship
- International Journal of Digital Curation
- ACM Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH)
- Heritage Science
- Information Technologies and International Development
- Journal of the Society of Archivists

⁵ Mahadevagoula, Rajashekhar and S, Pavithrabai M., "Recent Trends in Digital Library Publications: A Scientometric Analysis" (2022). Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal). 7058. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7058>

- Curator: The Museum Journal
- Visual Resources: An International Journal of Documentation
- Information Processing & Management
- Journal of Information Science (JIS)
- Library & Information Science Research
- Information Research
- Information Quarterly

5.6 Press releases and coverage

The purpose of the press releases is to document the key project development milestones. The first press release will report on the arrival of the ERA chair to the host institutions, the second on the formation of the research team, the third and fourth on the specific achievements of DISPATCHES, and the fifth on the final conference and overall project completion.

6 Exploitation framework

DISPATCHES is implemented within the remit of Open Science aiming to share the accumulated knowledge via open access publication, open datasets and methodologies. Within this the project will maintain a Results ownership list (ROL) and will follow the provisions of the Data Management Plan (D1.1.) as practical instruments of capturing useful exploitable results.

The initial exploitation benefits for different communities are captured in Table 9.

Table 9. Exploitation benefits for key target groups

Target Groups	Exploitation benefits
Cultural heritage professionals	New knowledge and educational materials on contributing to data spaces as data owners and utilizing data spaces as data consumers - intermediaries for end users.
Europeana	Contribute new research facilitating the deployment of the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage. Contributing useful knowledge to EAF and ENA.
Researchers and students	Methodologies and frameworks which can be developed in subsequent research.
Data space technologists	Lessons learned from the research on data space for Cultural Heritage.

Citizen scientists	Useful methods, practices, and toolkits which can be used in citizen science initiatives in the Cultural Heritage.
Governmental and Policy bodies, Agencies for Culture	Contribution to the delivery on national digitization activities within the National Recovery Plan.

Throughout the project lifecycle, we will refine the exploitation benefits and deliver a toolkit towards the end of the project which will make it easy to use relevant results in the future.

7 Conclusion

This deliverable presented a summary of the initial dissemination and communication planning of DISPATCHES and a summary of the activities delivered within the first six months of the project. It will serve as a basis for reporting on the subsequent dissemination and communication activities.

Appendix 1. IAB ToR

DISPATCHES International Advisory Board

Terms of Reference

1. Attending International Advisory Board (IAB) meetings in person or virtually to provide advice, share insights, and offer direction on DISPATCHES-related matters.
2. Participating in the Research Agenda setting activity.
3. Reviewing strategic plans, program developments, and key organizational decisions and providing feedback.
4. Proposing novel strategies to mobilize experts and resources, thereby fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and the exchange of knowledge.
5. Assist in identifying potential funding opportunities, strategic partnerships, and collaborations that align with the mission of DISPATCHES.
6. Providing advice on strategies to improve the relevance, dissemination, adoption, and use of research findings.
7. Advocating for DISPATCHES within your professional network and promoting its objectives to a larger audience.
8. Participating in two hiring committees and dissertation committees during the duration of the endeavour.
9. Maintaining the confidentiality of sensitive documents and information shared and discussed during International Advisory Board meetings.

Appendix 2. IAB Composition – some agreed and some to be asked

	NAME	PHOTO	BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH	DOMAIN	COUNTRY
ACCEPTED					
1	Dr Sandra Collins		<p>Dr Sandra Collins Is the Librarian to University College Dublin, taking up the role in March 2022. Formerly the Director of the National Library of Ireland (NLI), Dr Collins career spans 25 years in senior library, research and innovation roles across academic, industry and public sector organisations. She oversaw the acquisition of a number of world-class collections of papers and born-digital archives.</p> <p>She also instigated major digital collecting initiatives including over 300,000 Irish websites and the cataloguing/digitising of historical papers related to the Decade of Centenaries.</p> <p>Among her ambitious outreach projects is the 'Seamus Heaney: Listen Now Again' at the Bank of Ireland Cultural and Heritage Centre, and the Museum of Literature Ireland (MoLI), in partnership with UCD at Newman House.</p>	Libraries	Ireland
2	Prof. Panos Constantopoulos		<p>Professor in the Department of Informatics, Director of the MSc Programme in Digital Methods for the Humanities and former Dean of the School of Information Sciences and Technology, Athens University of Economics and Business. He is also affiliated with the Information Management Systems Institute of the "Athena" Research Centre, where he heads the Digital Curation Unit.</p>	Knowledge management	Greece

			He has been principal investigator or scientific responsible on the part of his affiliation in 40 national or international research and development projects. He is the coordinator of "APOLLONIS", the Greek Infrastructure for Digital Arts, Humanities and Language Research and Innovation. President of the Scientific Board of DARIAH ERIC.		
3	Prof. Monika Hagedorn-Saupe		Prof. Monika Hagedorn-Saupe studied mathematics, sociology, psychology, and education with a focus on adult education at the Ruhr-Universität Bochum, at Kings College London, and at the Freie Universität Berlin. She is president of CIDOC (the documentation committee in ICOM), president of the German Society for Information and Knowledge (DGI), serves as a member in the EC CEDCHE (Expert Group on a common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage), and is Vice President of the Michael Culture Association. She is professor in museology at the University of Applied Sciences HTW in Berlin/Germany.	Museology	Germany
4	Dr Suzanne Dumouchel		Suzanne Dumouchel, PhD in French literature, works in the Huma-Num unit, a large infrastructure for digital humanities. She leads the European project TRIPLE which aims to develop a platform for data discovery, research projects and researchers in SSH. She is co-coordinator of the European research infrastructure OPERAS, dedicated to Open Access scholarly communication in the	EOSC	France

			field of SSH. Strongly committed to the Open Science movement and to the promotion of research in SSH, she is particularly active in the field of research infrastructures. Director, EOSC Association (2021-23).		
5	Prof. Roberto Scopigno		Director of CNR-ISTI. He served as the former leader of the Visual Computing Lab, a research lab that he contributed to found in mid 1990. Plays a key role in developing the thinking around the European Cloud for Cultural Heritage.	3D, European cultural heritage cloud	Italy
6					
FURTHER POTENTIAL MEMBERS TO INVITE					
7	Tamar Evangelestia-Dougherty		Director of the Smithsonian Libraries and Archives. Previously an associate university librarian at Cornell University where she initiated Cornell RAD, a new research hub for rare and distinctive collections. As director of collections and services at New York Public Library's Schomburg Center for Research in Black Culture from 2013 to 2014, Evangelestia-Dougherty led collection and programmatic development of five curatorial divisions. At the University of Chicago's Black Metropolis Research Consortium, she served as executive director from 2011 to 2013 and as consulting archivist from 2007 to 2011. In addition to her extensive work with rare and distinctive collections, Evangelestia-Dougherty is a published author and public speaker who has presented nationally on topics of inclusivity and equity in	Special collections	USA

			bibliography, administration and primary-source literacy. She currently serves on the boards of Digital Scriptorium and the American Printing History Association.		
8	Harry Verwayen		General Director of Europeana Foundation. What he likes to do more than anything else though is to design and implement new business models that will change our way of thinking about heritage as an enabler of societal and economic growth. Quite taken lately by the developments of the sharing economy. A visual thinker, he needs a white board as much as a strong coffee. Mediocre football player, reasonable cook, aspiring photographer.	European data space for cultural heritage	The Netherlands
9	George Oates		<p>George Oates is a designer whose practice lies at the confluence of software, cultural heritage, and philosophy. As Executive Director and Founder of the Flickr Foundation, a 501c3 organization, George is leading efforts to guarantee that all the content on Flickr continues to be accessible in 100 years.</p> <p>George has been working online since 1996 and has had number of intriguing positions, including being a member of the small team that founded Flickr, project lead of Open Library at Internet Archive, and director of design at Stamen Design. George specializes in building systems for millions of individuals handling billions of objects, but George also enjoys developing extremely particular interfaces for small audiences. George's approach has always been focused on The Humans, and she takes</p>	Flickr Foundation	UK/USA

			pleasure in her ability to construct intelligible complicated systems		
10	Pier Luigi Sacco		<p>Pier Luigi Sacco is a distinguished scholar renowned for his groundbreaking research at the intersection of culture, economics, and technology. With a Ph.D. in economics from Stanford University, he is currently Professor of Economics at University of Chieti-Pescara, Senior Adviser to the OECD (Paris), Research Affiliate at the metaLAB (at) Harvard and at ISPC-CNR, Naples. His visionary work has focused on the impact of culture on economic systems and urban development, influencing policy discussions at national and international levels. He has served as Special Adviser of the European Commissioner for Education and Culture, a member of the Europeana Research Advisory Board, of the Economics of Culture Committee of the Italian Ministry of Culture, of the Advisory Council for Research & Innovation of the Czech Republic, and of the Advisory Council of Creative Georgia. He works and consults internationally in the fields of culture-led local development and is author of more than 200 papers in peer reviewed publication venues.</p>	University of Chieti-Pescara	Italy
11	Raivo Ruuslepp		<p>Raivo has a background in digital preservation, electronic records management and e-services development. He has been part of designing national policies for digital cultural heritage and information governance. He has been engaged in many European Union co-funded research and</p>	<u>EY Consultancy</u>	<u>Estonia</u>

			<p>development projects in and around data, records and digital curation (Durafire, 4C, E-Ark, DCH-RP, DC-Net, Protage, DPE), and is teaching library and records technology subjects at Tallinn University. Between 2012 to 2019 he worked for the National Library of Estonia serving much of that time as director of technical development at the library. He joined EY Consulting (Estonia) in 2018 as senior manager for digital transformations where he lead major consultancy work for a range of national and international clients including the European Commission and the Estonia Government.</p>		
--	--	--	---	--	--

